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Strengthening Internal Human Resources Management in Vehicle Registration and Identification Services at the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya

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Abstract

This research aims to examine strategies for increasing public trust through strengthening internal HR management in vehicle registration and identification services at the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya. The research uses a descriptive-qualitative approach. The method used is a qualitative approach. Based on literature studies and interpretation of research data, this research found that human resources management at the Vehicle Registration and Identification Subdirectorate of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya is still problematic. Apart from the problem of limited police personnel, there are lacks competence and slow digital transition in registration and identification services of the vehicle, which has an impact on the workload and professionalism of the police in serving the needs of the community. Therefore, there are eight human resources management models as a strategy to increase public trust in the quality of the registration and identification services of the vehicle at the Polda Metro Jaya, including: legality, integrity, efficiency, effectiveness, involvement, firmness, transparency, and justice.

Keywords: Public Trust, HR Management, Vehicle Registration and Identification, Public Service, Digital Transition

1. Introduction

A survey result released by the Indonesian Survey Institute (LSI) in March 2023, showed that the level of public trust in the Indonesian National Police was the lowest compared to four other law enforcement agencies. The National Police got 64%, an increase of 10% from the survey in August 2022, but still far below the Prosecutor's Office, Corruption Eradication Commission and the courts which were above 70% (Katadata.co.id, March 2nd, 2023). Public trust in the Bhayangkara Corps began to recover in mid-2023. The results of the Indonesian Political Indicators (IPI) survey show that the level of public trust in the National Police reached 76.4% (Tribatanews.com, July 2nd, 2023). This shows the dynamics of public assessment and perception of the

reputation and performance of the National Police which relies on various forms of service in all sectors, as well as being a source of legitimacy for the police.

Police legitimacy is an important issue in the democratic era when the police are increasingly integrated with society. In this era, policing has become so open and involving the public, inclusive of various groups and layers of society, as a source of legitimacy for the police itself (Paterson & Williams, 2018: 87). Furthermore, Skolnick (1999) emphasized that policing practices in this era can be realized by emphasizing two important aspects, namely openness and accountability. The key to democratic policing lies in the legitimacy of the public who are the object of police security (Karnavian & Sulisty, 2017).

One sector that is also a barometer of public legitimacy is services related to requesting or providing vehicle documents in the form of Vehicle Registration Certificates (Surat Tanda Nomor Kendaraan or STNK) and Vehicle Ownership Book (Buku Pemilik Kendaraan Bermotor or BPKB) to the public. Ownership of a vehicle certificate is important because it is proof of vehicle administration. As the owners of the vehicle is increasing from time to time, it is inevitable that ownership of a STNK and BPKB will become a prerequisite for vehicle ownership. According to dataindonesia.id, vehicles in Indonesia have increased by 5.7% since 2020 (Mahdi, 2022). Based on National Police data, the Regional Police (Polda) with the largest number of vehicles is the East Java Police, followed by the Metro Jaya Police (Mahdi, 2022). The number of vehicles in 14 areas of Polda Metro Jaya territory reached 22.09 million units with motorbikes being the largest unit at 17,621,463 units.

In accordance with the regulations of Law no. 22 of 2009 on Road Traffic and Transportation there are various requirements that must be fulfilled so that a person can be said to be legally eligible to drive a vehicle. First, drivers are required to have a driving license to be able to drive a vehicle on the road. Second, the STNK is used to register new vehicles. Third, registration of new vehicles must also have a BPKB and a Vehicle Number (Tanda Nomor Kendaraan Bermotor or TNKB).

A driver must carry a Driver's license, STNK, BPKB, and TNKB when using their vehicle on traffic lanes. This requirement is issued by the Indonesian National Police through the vehicle registration and identification management system. For the Jakarta area and its surroundings, this authority lies with Polda Metro Jaya, especially in the Sub-directorate of Registration and Identification. Based on Police Regulation no. 14 of 2018 on the Organizational Structure and Work Procedures of Regional Police, the Sub-directorate of registration and identification has the task of organizing and fostering the implementation of registration and identification of vehicles, Driver's license, STNK, BPKB, as well as facilitating those documents. The implementation of these tasks is carried out through a one-stop administration system as regulated under Presidential Regulation No. 5 of 2015 on the Implementation of a One-Stop Administration System (Sistem Administrasi Manunggal Satu Atap or Samsat). Samsat is used to register and extend STNK, BPKB and TNKB.

Services through Samsat currently continue to develop along with progress, especially those related to technological developments. In 2019, the National Police launched National Online Samsat in seven provinces (Ravel, 2019), then it was upgraded and replaced with the National Digital Samsat application (Signal). At Polda Metro Jaya itself, service improvements are no less dynamic. Apart from using online applications to provide services to extend STNK, BPKB, and TNKB, the Samsat of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya also provides Samsat Drive Thru and Mobile Samsat services which are open in locations that are easy for the public to reach.

Police services in the registration and identification sector have proven to make things easier and more satisfying for the public. Based on the Community Satisfaction Index, the Samsat of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya managed to get an Community Satisfaction Index score of 84.14 for BPKB and 83.46 for STNK (Polda Metro Jaya, 2022a), or an average Community Satisfaction Index of 83.80. This achievement proves that the service innovation by the Registration and Identification Sub-directorate of Samsat Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya has received quite good recognition from the public. This means that public legitimacy towards the police is very high because in principle the public believes that the police can solve their problems and rights in the vehicle traffic sector.

Even though externally the services of the Vehicle Registration and Identification Subdirector of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya have received quite good reviews and trust from the public, internally the Polda Metro Jaya itself stated that improvements still need to be made. This can be seen through the Government Agency Performance Report (LKIP) where the realization of IKM results (83.80) is still below the target of 84 (Polda Metro Jaya, 2022a). This reality certainly demands an evaluation of the internal HR management of the Vehicle Registration and Identification Subdirector of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya so that service quality can be improved. Moreover, the number of vehicles in the DKI Jakarta area continues to grow, so the police must be able to provide services and coordinate between agencies more effectively and efficiently (Polda Metro Jaya, 2022a).

Data shows that internally, the Vehicle Registration and Identification Subdirector of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya is facing the problem of inequality between the availability of human resources (HR) and the number of STNK and BPKB handled every day. Data from Government Agency Performance Accountability Report (Laporan Akuntabilitas Kinerja Instansi Pemerintah or LKIP) shows that the total number of personnel from the Vehicle Registration and Identification Subdirector of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya is 1,414 people, while services for STNK and BPKB in 2021 will reach 4,808,287 services (Polda Metro Jaya, 2022b). The ratio of personnel to services is 1:3,400. This means that one personnel in the Subdirector of registration and identification of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya handles 3,400 STNK and BPKB.

The impact of this inequality is a high workload which can open up various deviant practices which ultimately affect the public's view of the national police professionalism, especially the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya. This is made worse by the condition that in the SOP for STNK and BPKB services at Polda Metro Jaya, it is stated that it only takes 2-3 hours. The fact that the ratio of the number of human resources to the number of service requests is very unequal, means it is impossible to provide services according to the SOP. In reality, the implementation of services according to the SOP can only be partially fulfilled, around 300 files per day. The remaining files cannot meet the standards according to the Standard Operating Procedure.

This reality proves that the condition of human resources at the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya is the opposite of the positive perception of the community regarding Samsat services. Suwanda (2020) in his research at the Detective Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya found that HR management variables and organizational culture had a significant relationship with service quality. It is urgent to add quality police personnel, facilities and infrastructure, incentives beyond basic salary, and position promotions to encourage professionalism and quality of service at Samsat.

Departing from the reality above, this research seeks to find a strategy to overcome the imbalance between the availability of human resources and public expectations through human resource management, coordination, and professionalism. On the other hand, it is necessary to consider the challenges and opportunities for change along with technological developments towards the digitalization of public services. It is important for service excellence in police services to create a professional system that upholds speed, accuracy, friendliness, and comfort. The ability of the Indonesian National Police to consistently meet and exceed community expectations is a benchmark for their success in resolving problems and increasing public trust.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Democratic Policing

One of the main figures in the development of the concept of democratic policing, Jerome H Skolnick (1999:2) stated, "...democratic police forces are not supposed to be insular, self-contained, or cut off from the communities from which their power derives. Openness to the free and the poor should be a master ideal of democratic policing." This statement emphasizes that democratic policing requires openness and public participation, inclusiveness of various groups and levels of society as a source of police legitimacy. Furthermore,

Skolnick emphasized that democratic policing practices can be realized by emphasizing two important aspects, namely openness and accountability.

Democratic policing then provides guidance for the police to pay attention to community problems and further collaborate with the community to gain legitimacy. Experts accentuate that democratic policing is a concept that emphasizes that the police are the public and the public is the police, where there is inclusive cooperation between the community and the police. The key to democratic policing lies in public legitimacy, which means the community is the object of police security (Karnavian & Sulisty, 2017).

According to Jeremy Travis (Roberson & Mire, 2009), the characteristics of the democratic policing conception contain several important notes. First, the police must work in accordance with democratic principles, namely being professional, understanding human rights standards, and acting in accordance with legal provisions. Second, the police as the holder of the community's mandate, are professional, refer to the law, and uphold ethical values and norms that apply in society and institutions. Third, the police must have top priority in securing and protecting people's lives. Fourth, the police always serve the community selflessly and are responsible to the community. Fifth, that the protection provided by the police to life and property is the primary function of other police operations. Sixth, police actions must be in accordance with human dignity and human rights. Lastly, in carrying out their duties the police should act neutrally and not discriminate.

Basically, the essence of understanding democratic policing is the consent from the community. A prerequisite for building community support is providing transparency in police operations, and cultivating communication and mutual understanding with the public that the police serve. Within this framework, matters relating to police organization and issue management are regulated by the state. Managerial includes command direction; regulations in supervision; the composition of the police force; the rights of police personnel; and provision of adequate resources and training. Good management will influence the public's legitimacy towards the police.

2.2. *Police Legitimacy*

Mazerolle et al. (2013) in their work entitled "Legitimacy in Policing: A Systematic Review" conducted a meta-analysis of various studies related to the legitimacy of police institutions and identified various processes that influence and shape police legitimacy. Based on this analysis, Mazerolle et al. identified five pathways to police legitimacy, namely:

1. *Procedural Justice*

A person's perception of the treatment received during the decision-making process. In this case, how does the police implement their powers in a fair manner and in accordance with applicable regulations.

2. *Performance*

Public confidence in the police, both directly and in perceptions of police performance. Even though it is proven that there is a link between performance and legitimacy, the impact of the link between procedural justice and police legitimacy is more significant.

3. *Distributive Justice*

Distributive justice or social justice is defined as the perception of fairness of police services and the intensity of police activities among various groups, communities, and social classes. Ethnicity, age and economic status are proven to have an important role in building perceptions of police fairness and police legitimacy.

4. *Legality*

Legality is understood as the perception of applicable law and criminal justice. Public distrust will greatly influence the legitimacy of the police in the eyes of the public. Legal legitimacy is an important antecedent factor for community cooperation and compliance with the police.

5. *Tradition/Culture*

This aspect can be understood as the role of the police as a symbolic and traditional representative of public order and social cohesion.

2.3. Public Trust

Trust is one of the keys to building relationships with individuals, companies and society. Trust refers to a high assessment of the competence, honesty, or reliability of a trusted person, in accordance with expectations or norms (Kleinnijenhuis, van Hoof, and Oegema, 2006). As an inconstant quality, trust is subjective and even emotional depending on environmental conditions, institutions and the actors involved.

Public trust itself is citizens' trust in the state and government, including its institutions, policies and officials (Widaningrum, 201). The higher the public's trust in an institution, the stronger the legitimacy of the institution in carrying out its duties and the public is more willing to be involved in these activities (Castillo, et al., 2011). Public trust in the police is essentially related to the integrity of administration and performance of police services. The hypothesis put forward by several experts states that the higher the public's trust and satisfaction with the performance of state institutions, the better the governance system (Boukaert and de Walle, 2003).

The existence of public trust has implications for several aspects (Fukuyama, 1995; Bouckaert & de Walle, 2003). First, trust is an efficient way to lower transaction costs in social, economic and political relationships. If the public has high trust in the government, the process of making public policies will be simpler and faster. Second, encourage the public to respect the authority of public officials so that the process of formulating government policies and activities becomes easier. Third, improve relations between government and society. When the relationship between the government and society becomes closer, there will be a sense of mutual respect between each other, thereby reducing or eliminating feelings of suspicion between society and the government in implementing policies (Widaningrum, 2017).

2.4. Public Service

Public service is the process of fulfilling needs through the activities of other people directly (Moenir, 2002:16). Public services are all services by government agencies and state institutions in the form of goods or services to meet community needs in accordance with law, including three groups of services: (1) administrative; (2) goods; and (3) services (Minister of State Apparatus Utilization Decree No. 63/2003). Public service indicators cover several main things (Bittner et al., 2022):

1. *Tangibles*, namely physical facilities, equipment, employees, and communication facilities owned by the service provider.
2. *Reliability*, namely the ability to provide promised services accurately.
3. *Responsiveness*, namely the willingness to help service users and provide services sincerely.
4. *Assurance* is the knowledge, politeness, and ability of officers to give trust to service users.
5. *Empathy* is the ability to provide attention to individual service users.

In terms of public services, something that is quite important to develop is service excellence, namely the service provided exceeds the expectations of customers (Gouthier, Giese, & Bartl, 2012). This means that the police must ensure that human resources (HR) are available to provide satisfaction to the community because they get more benefits when served.

2.5. Human Resources Management

Human resources are the most important asset for an organization (Drucker, 2007). When an organization loses quality human resources, it can affect the investment made by the organization. To produce superior human resources is not easy; requires intensive education, training, and coaching. On this basis, HR management is needed to manage the HR of an organization. HR management includes aspects of planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling HR in the organization (Rivai and Sagala, 2013). Increasing HR capabilities is important to achieve competitive advantage which can be achieved through special tools, namely integrated HR management policies, programs, and practices. By managing human resources well, organizational goals can be achieved. Not only in terms of the availability of competent resources, but it can also increase customer satisfaction, a healthy organizational culture and guaranteed employee welfare (Hanoum & Noufal, 2009).

3. Research Method

This type of research is descriptive research using a qualitative approach (Walidin, Saifullah & Tabrani, 2015). The phenomenon observed in this study is the service provided by the Vehicle Registration and Identification Sub directorate of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya in increasing public trust. (*public trust*).

Researchers use data collection techniques through library studies to examine and explore literature, scientific notes, and documents relevant to the research topic, for example books, journals, scientific articles, theses, and other sources. Sugiyono (2007) states that there are three sources for literature studies based on their content. First, primary sources. This comes from original articles written by people who experienced, observed or did it themselves. For example, journal, theses/dissertations, research reports, reports, publications, catalogues, and interview results. Second, secondary sources, namely any publications written by the author that are not the result of direct observation of the events described. For example, encyclopaedias, textbooks, dictionaries, and handbooks. Finally, tertiary sources that can be used as initial information and for further research. For example, index, abstract and bibliography.

Data that has been collected through literature review will be analysed using inductive reasoning. Inductive analysis is a general conclusion drawn based on knowledge about specific matters or theories and concepts that are built (Kalof, Dan, & Dietz, 2008). To validate the data, the researcher used data triangulation techniques. This technique is carried out by verifying whether certain data is indeed true (Afrizal, 2014). Triangulation is a technique used to check the validity of existing data by using something else for comparative data (Moleong, 2014). According to Denzin & Lincoln (2000), triangulation is a step in integrating various data sources, researchers, theories, and methods. Based on the theoretical basis and research methodology above, the analytical framework for this research can be described as shown in the following figure:

Figure 3.1: Analysis Framework

Source: Author's Processed Results (2023)

4. Research Results and Discussion

4.1. Optimizing Human Resources Limitation

The availability of human resources (HR) in the vehicle registration and identification sector at the registration and identification sub directorate of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya is very limited. Polda Metro Jaya data for 2022 records that the number of personnel at the Polda Metro Jaya Samsat Office is only 831 people. Of this number, the largest number of personnel has the rank of Brigadier, namely 688 personnel (82.8%), while the others consist of civil servants as many as 83 people (9.9%), Inspector One (19 people), Inspector Two (28 people), and Assistant Commissioner of Police (13 people). Of the 831 personnel, 4.20

million vehicle registrations must be processed. Meanwhile, the number of personnel that handle BPKB is 694 people out of a total of 1,198,627 BPKB issued within a period of seven months, from July 2022 to January 2023. In 2022, the number of personnel handlings STNK and BPKB was 1,525 people, and they handled and issued 5.4 million STNK and BPKB. This number of personnel had increased from the 2021 record. In 2021, there were 1,414 people serving 4,808,287 STNK and BPKB issuances (Polda Metro Jaya, 2022b). This data implicitly shows that there is a tendency to increase the number of vehicles so that new registration and identification are necessary. According to data from Polda Metro Jaya, the number of two-wheeled and four-wheeled vehicles was 22.62 million in 2022.

The types of services and number of personnel serving registration and identification in the 14 jurisdictions of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya are as shown below:

Table 4.1: Types of Service and Number of Personnel

STNK SERVICES	AMOUNT
PA	59
BBN 1	111
BBN 2	78
Perp/Sah	113
Tu	111
Mutasi	53
Arsdok	24
Cek Fisik	71
Tnkb	19
Putor	45
Ba Mat	40
Samling	25
Gerai	33
Drive Thru	19
Door to Door	-
Yanduan	10
Lain2	20
Total	831
BPKB SERVICES	
Total personnel	307
Dikbangspes	13
Sertifikasi BPKB	48
Data BKP	34
Yanpim	10
TU/Register	72
BBN 1 Pendaftaran	87
BBN 3 Perubahan	61
Mutasi ID	14
Selra	14
Ardok	34
Total	694
Grand total	1.525

Source: Polda Metro Jaya (2022)

The availability of adequate human resources is not the only factor that determines excellent service quality. However, it cannot be denied that the number of personnel serving the needs of the community will greatly influence the process of issuing STNK and BPKB. Referring to Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public

Services, it is stated that excellent service is service that is fast, easy, certain, cheap and accountable. This means that excellent service requires adequate personnel so that the flow and process of issuing STNK and BPKB takes place quickly. Too few human resources tend to put more workload on personnel, which can reduce the quality of service and affect the level of public satisfaction.

Data released by the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya in 2022 shows that the personnel workload is quite large because they must provide up to 2,500 STNK registration and identification services every day and the lowest is 251 registration and identification services. Likewise, with BPKB services. Data from the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya for 2023 recorded that there were 1,198,627 BPKB issued within a period of seven months, from July 2022 to January 2023. Registrations for changing owners counted 344,400, new vehicle registrations were 595,000, BPKB registrations for changes were 112,387, BPKB duplicates registrations were 2,054, BPKB registration for mutations outside the region were 144,786.

High workloads that are not balanced with strong mental preparedness not only result in less effective services but are also tiring for both the personnel themselves and the people who need the services. As illustrated in the following data, services that tend to increase will cause problems if they are not balanced with the availability of personnel.

Table 4.2: Number of Services and Personnel Availability

SAMSAT	SERVICE/DAY	AMOUNT OF PERSONNEL			
		POLRI	PEMDA	J.R.	DKI
Central Jakarta	1000-2500	55	12	15	
North Jakarta	1000-2500	58	20	6	
West Jakarta	1000-2500	74	59	7	41
South Jakarta	1000-2500	112	17	9	26
East Jakarta	1000-2500	112	42	18	
Tangerang City	751-1000	38	30	2	
Ciledug	751-1000	32	16	2	
Serpong	251-499	23	51	3	
Ciputat	751-1000	40	23	3	
Kelapa Dua	751-1000	30	22	3	
Bekasi City	1000-1500	82	27	9	
Bekasi Regency	1000-1500	52	20	4	
Depok City	1000-1500	78	22	2	
Cinere	251-500	47	17	1	
TOTAL		833	378	84	67

Source: Polda Metro Jaya (2022)

Polri means Indonesian National Police, Pemda means Regional Police, J.R means Jasa Raharja (insurance company that emphasizes service to victims of road traffic accidents and public passengers), DKI means Special Capital District of Jakarta

When personnel resources are limited, it is necessary to carry out professional HR management. In this case, the Sub registration and identification of the Polda Metro Jaya Traffic Directorate needs to have an HR development and management strategy to manage personnel well. HR management can include planning, organizing, implementing, and controlling human resources in an organization (Rivai and Sagala, 2013). Human resources (HR) are the most important assets for an organization. When an agency loses one of its good human resources, it will certainly affect the investment that the agency has spent. They must look for new candidates who are not necessarily equal to or much better than the first. Therefore, it is necessary to optimize the limited human resources in the scope of Vehicle Registration and Identification Sub directorate of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya to manage and maintain existing human resources through strengthening competence.

The competency aspect of police personnel is one of the normative standards for policing which has an impact on the performance of handling registration and identification administration. According to Law No. 13 of 2003 on Employment, competency is the work ability of each individual which includes aspects of knowledge, skills and work attitudes that are in accordance with established standards. As Gunarto said, differences in competency and human resources between fellow members of the National Police often become obstacles in implementation in the field. It is necessary to improve the paradigm and professionalism of police personnel so that they are able to serve the community well. Competence is of course closely related to the quality of human resources possessed by the police. Competency is directly related to experience, motivation, personality characteristics, emotional strength, intellectual ability and organizational culture (Noor, 2021).

According to the Decree of the Traffic Director of Polda Metro Jaya in 2018 on Service Standards for Issuing Vehicle Ownership Book (BPKB), the quality of service processes and service products needs to be supported by officers who are competent in their field of duty and whose service behaviour is skilled, fast, precise, polite, accompanied by clean facilities and infrastructure. There are 10 competencies that are expected to be possessed by the personnel of Vehicle Registration and Identification Sub directorate of Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya, including:

1. Holds the rank of Officer/Brigadier/PNS;
2. Friendly, polite, and able to communicate well;
3. Mastering the procedures and mechanisms for issuing BPKB and STNK;
4. Mastering traffic rules correctly;
5. Have a Vocational Education certificate for Vehicle Registration and Identification;
6. Able to master education and training in vehicle registration and identification;
7. Mastering quality in the field of vehicle registration and identification services
8. Mastering verbal communication;
9. Able to operate a computer;
10. Able to work in a team.

One of the competency indicators that is quite important is Vocational Education certification for vehicle registration and identification. In a Hearing Meeting with Commission III of the Indonesian House of Representatives on July 5th, 2023, the Head of the National Police Traffic Corps (Korlantas) Inspector General Pol Firman Shantyabudi said that there were still very few police officers who had certification in the traffic sector compared to other fields (Kompas.com, July 5th, 2023). If certification is a prerequisite for the competency of a police personnel, then it should be encouraged that the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya prepares human resources to take part in special education and training regarding the vehicle registration system. In this way, the quality of vehicle registration services is getting better.

On the other hand, internal supervision is also needed to maintain standard operational procedures in accordance with statutory provisions. In accordance with the Decree of the Traffic Director of Polda Metro Jaya of 2018 on Service Standards for Issuing Vehicle Ownership Books (BPKB), supervision can be carried out by direct superiors in stages through orders and carried out continuously. As shown in the following data tabulation, the composition of structural positions is sufficient to determine and ensure the implementing and supervisory components. From the existing composition, it can be concluded that most personnel assigned to the vehicle registration and identification system are police with the rank of Brigadier. They are referred to as executors, while the rank of Assistant Commissioner of Police act as supervisors. As an officer, Assistant Commissioner of Police has a role in managing and leading their subordinates, including providing direction, guidance, and evaluating performance and leading operations.

Table 4.3: Rank and Number of Personnel of the Registration and Identification Sub directorate of Polda Metro Jaya

RANK	AMOUNT
Assistant Commissioner of Police (AKBP)	-
Police commissioner (KOMPOL)	-

Assistant Commissioner of Police (AKP)	13
First Police Inspector (IPTU)	19
Second Police Inspector (IPDA)	28
BRIGADIER (BRIGADIR)	688
civil servants	83
Casual Daily Employees	-
Total	831

Source: Polda Metro Jaya (2022)

4.2. Digital Transition in Registration and Identification Services

Public service quality indicators are determined by the service itself. When a service is not optimal and causes complaints and dissatisfaction from customers or the public, transformation and innovation are needed to solve the problem. Complaints that generally occur in vehicle registration and identification services include long queues, long registration processes and a hierarchical service room structure (Dwiyanto, 2011). Problems that arise in the registration and identification service model often force people to use the services of brokers. The structure of the service counter is made so that officers can sit comfortably, while the public must stand and even bend when communicating, so it gives the impression that comfort is provided for the officers, not for the public.

The parameter of excellent public service is the ability of police personnel to understand what the community needs. The indicators are being able to meet standards, speed, precision, accuracy, and transparency. The success of excellent service must be measured, assessing the level of its ability to achieve community satisfaction, right on target according to what the community needs and wants. In order to achieve public trust, not only the competence of police personnel must be improved, but operational processes and management also need to be improved. Finally, the idea of one stop service or what is known as one roof service emerged. The implementation of this service is basically to increase efficiency and effectiveness by minimizing geographical distance between related functions, thereby shortening the time required for the service process, it also becomes easier for service users to obtain services. (Hardiyansyah, 2011).

In the National Police organization, there is something known as the One-Stop Single Administration System (Samsat). Samsat is a collaborative system between the National Police and the Provincial Revenue Service and PT. Jasa Raharja (Persero). Formed in 1976 as an effort to improve regional services and income through vehicle taxes. According to the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2015 concerning the Implementation of a Single One-Stop Administration System for Vehicles, which is the implementing regulation of Article 67 Paragraph (4) of Law Number 22 of 2009 on Road Traffic and Transportation, Samsat carries out the Registration and Identification of Vehicles, payment of Taxes, Transfer of Name Fees, and payment of Mandatory Contributions to Traffic Accident Funds and Road Transport in an integrated manner.

Responding to the needs of an increasingly modern society, an electronic service system has now emerged that makes it easier for vehicle owners to register and pay taxes. To be precise, in August 2021, the National Police released an application called National Digital Samsat or Signal (Pajak.com, 22 August 2021). Signal is an improvement on the National Online Samsat (Samolnas) application which was launched first but still has errors. Through this system, the process of validating annual STNK, paying vehicle tax, and mandatory contributions to road traffic accident funds (SWDKLLJ) becomes easy. Signal utilizes artificial intelligence technology for facial recognition of application users which is connected to the Population and Civil Registry (Dukcapil) database. The data will be compared with the National Police Traffic Corps' electronic registration and identification (ERI) database (Kompas.com, September 3rd, 2023).

Long before the existence of Signal, since 2016, Polda Metro Jaya has innovated vehicle registration and identification services through an electronic system. Especially at the South Jakarta Police, there is a South Jakarta Samsat system which was launched on June 22nd, 2016. Then a year later a vehicle data and tax information application were also launched at the Traffic Directorate of the Metro Jaya Police through an

application and web service. It doesn't stop there; the South Jakarta Police continue to innovate by launching a Digital Samsat and Non-Cash Payment system in 2028. Three years ago, on September 22nd, 2020 to be precise, Polda Metro Jaya released the SI ONDEL application as an electronic system for recording data and registration and identification information.

In 2017, the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya also launched the Integrated BPKB System. Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya collaborates with Civil Registry Service Office, brand holder agents and financing institutions to create system-integrated digital services. This system allows applicants to get fast, safe, and transparent services. This system provides 12 stages that make it easier for people to register (*Prolegalnews*, November 20th, 2017).

The digital service support implemented by the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya has had a huge impact on the quality of public services. According to a PosKota report dated November 10th, 2022, there have been extraordinary changes in the vehicle registration and identification service system at Polda Metro Jaya. In contrast to the previous eight years, Vehicle Registration and Identification services are getting faster and easier. People no longer need to queue or wait for a long time to apply for STNK and BPKB.

The existence of this digital system is an implementation of the National Police's transformation in the service sector by presenting modern and quality services in accordance with the vision of Presisi (predictive, responsible, transparent, fair) or a National Police that can predict future community needs, has a sense of social responsibility and is at the same time able to work in a transparent and fair manner. Excellent service in the digital era is supported by a technology system that is controlled, commanded, evaluated, monitored, communicated through the back office.

However, the public has not really utilized the available digital services to register and identify vehicles. Apart from problems in using the application, it is also because the transition process towards digitalization is slow (*Detikfinance.com*, June 6th, 2023). People are still worried about losing money when making payments via the online system. This is because the system in applications such as Signal is not yet stable and safe. The loss of public trust in online applications is also driven by the increasingly widespread phenomenon of fraud. On this basis, people ultimately tend to take care of it directly at the Samsat office rather than through the application. Even if they want to get results easily, they prefer to use the services of brokers even though they have to pay 2-3 times more.

This discourse that develops in society then influences the level of public trust in the National Police institution. On the one hand, the public is satisfied with the services provided, which can be seen in the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM) survey which is quite high (above 80%), but on the other hand, it is necessary to maintain public trust so that the National Police institution becomes more legitimate and trustworthy.

4.3. Strengthening Human Resources Management to Increase Public Trust

Every organization or state institution certainly has a noble goal, namely serving the community. In the democratic era, when the constitutional system is increasingly open, public participation and involvement in the functions and responsibilities of the state is increasingly high. Of course, society has now become oriented towards state service. On this basis, the National Police as a state institution should make the community the center of its services. In the democratic policing paradigm, the police must work in accordance with democratic principles, namely being professional, understanding human rights standards, ethical values and norms, respecting human dignity, and serving society without selflessness or discrimination (Roberson & Mire, 2009). When there is no longer a wall of separation between the police and the community, the police organization will become more legitimate and trusted.

Nashar (2020) emphasized that service quality will increase public trust. Services that are maximal, effective, efficient and answer community needs will receive feedback in the form of satisfaction and positive perceptions, thus building stronger legitimacy in society. This satisfaction is built on the basis of maximum performance and

positive perceptions are formed due to adequate service quality. When public trust and legitimacy are higher, the duties and responsibilities of the police will become easier because the public will be more obedient in carrying out the provisions set by the police. However, it must be noted that trust does not form by itself. Not only optimal performance or service quality, but it must be supported by integrity, transparency and accountability created in a service. Apart from that, it is also supported by facilities, certainty, accuracy, responsiveness, and empathy (Bittner et al., 2022).

Empathy is an important issue in measuring the quality or performance of a public service. This is closely related to the attitudes and ways of communication that take place between the police and the community (Oxburgh, 2012). The police must ensure reasonable and professional behaviour in serving the public. Physically, the completeness of services in the form of the availability of personnel, media and equipment as well as a comfortable place also determines the quality of a public service. Registration and identification officers at the Traffic Directorate Polda Metro Jaya must also be able to provide the best service through procedures that are easy and not complicated, fast and transparent. When there are complaints or difficulties, officers should take the initiative to ask questions and then provide practical solutions. In this way, the people served are assured that their needs will be met within a short time.

In order to increase public trust, the important thing to do is strengthen HR management in the internal police sphere (Arninsi, 2017). As the core organ of a public service, competent and professional human resource management in its field is very much needed. This is in line with the Decree of the Assistant Chief of Police for Human Resources Number KEP/620/VI/2020 dated May 27th, 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan for National Police Human Resources for 2020-2024. According to this Strategic Plan, developing and strengthening human resources is important because the root of the problem of bureaucratic reform lies in human resources, where the allocation in terms of quantity, quality, and distribution according to territory is unbalanced, and productivity levels are still low. It is necessary to strengthen the HR management system so that the National Police's human resources have integrity, competence, capability, professionalism, high performance, and prosperity. Therefore, if these qualities are met, excellent public services will be created. The way to do this is by adding quality police personnel, facilities and infrastructure, incentives other than basic salary and position promotions. In addition, to strengthen organizational culture, it is necessary to develop democratic leadership, minimize intervention, and increase coordination between levels of positions (Suwanda, 2020).

Human resource management development can also be carried out through education, training and certification, and experience in the field. There are eight HR management models that can be encouraged to increase public trust.

1. *Legality*

The police work based on legal logic and not based on beliefs and other assessments of a legal issue. In terms of public services, the police must ensure that all procedures, mechanisms and stages in processing registration and identification of vehicles comply with applicable SOPs and legal provisions. There is no room for interpretation for the police to act arbitrarily just because of personal assumptions or beliefs.

2. *Integrity*

Integrity in public services is a necessity. Without integrity, it is difficult for the public to have confidence in police services. There will always be concerns so that people tend to choose shortcuts in processing registration and identification. This concern could arise due to services that are not optimal or could be in the form of a belief that the police tend to be corrupt in their work.

3. *Efficiency*

Digital service breakthroughs should be a refinement of physical services in the office. Don't let digital services become inefficient because it makes it more difficult and complicated for people to access vehicle registration and identification services.

4. *Effectiveness*

Vehicle registration and identification services should be right on target and directly aimed at solving problems, not on the contrary creating new problems because people must wait too long without certainty regarding the registration and identification of their vehicles.

5. *Involvement*

The police must be involved in solving problems faced by the community. If there are problems, help find a solution as soon as possible. If necessary, the police go into the community to provide closer service.

6. *Dependability*

The police must serve the community from start to finish. There should be no impression of half-hearted service. Persistence in public service will have an impact on performance because they will work until completion.

7. *Transparency*

Strategic initiatives for providing digital services are one of the instruments for implementing the principle of transparency in public services. When public services become more transparent, the public will immediately trust them more.

8. *Fairness*

Public services must reach all and for all. There is no discrimination, ideological barriers, or gaps in social status. Everyone must be served according to their individual needs and interests.

5. **Conclusion**

Based on the description and discussion above, several important conclusions can be drawn in this research. First, it is necessary to optimize the limited police human resources to improve the quality of vehicle registration and identification services at the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya. Optimizing human resources is not only by increasing the number of personnel, but also by strengthening competence. Second, it is necessary to accelerate the digital transition in vehicle registration and identification services at the Traffic Directorate Polda Metro Jaya so that it can reduce the workload of limited police personnel. Finally, there are eight HR management models that can be encouraged to increase public trust in the quality of vehicle registration and identification services at the Sub-registration and identification of the Traffic Directorate of Polda Metro Jaya, including: legality, integrity, efficiency, effectiveness, involvement, firmness, transparency, and fairness.

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